

Seasonal monitoring of Durankulak Lake using Sentinel 2 Data

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Abstract: Durankulak Lake is part of the European Ecological Network of NATURA2000 and a Ramsare Convention Site for the wetlands. The protected site covers an area of 446.5 ha. It is one of the well-preserved coastal wetlands in Bulgaria with international importance for the protection of over 260 endemic, rare and endangered species of plants and animals. One of the problems of the lake, as well as of many other wetlands in Bulgaria is the excessive reed overgrowth. Regular monitoring is necessary for protection and maintenance of this wetland therefore satellite data have a great advantage. This study monitored the lake for the period - December 2019 - July 2020, including three seasons - winter, spring and summer. Satellite data from Sentinel 2A and Sentinel 2B were used. One satellite image was used for each month. Pre-processing of the satellite data was made and spectral indices were generated. The results obtained show the development and condition of the vegetation in Durankulak Lake. NDVI was generated in order to assess the vegetation in the lake. The orthogonal transformation model called Tasseled Cap Transformation (TCT) has also been used. This is a model for classifying and analyzing the processes related to the dynamics of changes, affecting the main components of the earth's surface: soil, vegetation and water. The results show the development of Durankulak Lake for the period of the observed three seasons, which assess its condition and changes that occur in a short monitored period.

Сезонен мониторинг на езерото Дуранкулак, с използването на данни от Сентинел 2

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Ключови думи: сателитни данни, влажни зони, мониторинг, динамика

Резюме: Езерото Дуранкулак е част от Европейската екологична мрежа на NATURA2000. То е и част от Рамсарската конвенция за влажните зони. Защитеният обект обхваща площ от 446,5 хектара. Това е една от най-добре запазените крайбрежни влажни зони в България с международно значение за опазването на над 260 ендемични, редки и застрашени видове растения и животни. Един от проблемите на езерото, както и на много други влажни зони в България, е прекомерното обрастване на тръстика и намаляване на откритите водни площи. Необходимо е извършването на редовен мониторинг за опазването и поддържането на тази влажна зона. Спътниковите данни имат голямо предимство за това. Настоящото проучване наблюдава езерото за периода от декември 2019 г. до юли 2020 г. Това включва три сезона - зима, пролет и лято. Използвани са спътникови данни от Sentinel 2A и Sentinel 2B. За всеки месец е използвано по едно спътниково изображение, според достъпните налични. Направена е предварителна обработка на спътниковите данни, след което са използвани спектрални индекси. Техните резултати показват развитието и динамиката на езерото Дуранкулак. Индексът NDVI е използван за оценка на растителността в езерото. Използван е и модел на ортогонална трансформация, наречен Tasseled Cap Transformation (TCT). Това е модел за класифициране и анализ на процесите, свързани с динамиката на промените, засягащи основните компоненти на земната повърхност: почва, растителност и вода. Резултатите показват развитието на езерото Дуранкулак за периода от наблюдаваните три сезона, което оценя състоянието му и промените, които се случват за кратък наблюдаван период.

Introduction

Durankulak Lake is part of the European Ecological Network of NATURA2000. It is a Ramsare Convention Site. The protected site covers an area of 446.5 ha. It is one of the well-preserved coastal wetlands in Bulgaria with international importance for the protection of over 260 endemic, rare and endangered species of plants and animals.

Durankulak Lake Protected area is situated in the northeastern part of Bulgaria, about 6 km from the Bulgarian-Romanian border and 15 km north of the town of Shabla. It was announced by Order No. 123 / 21.02.1980 of the Committee for Protection of the Natural Environment. It has a management plan developed by the Ministry of Environment and Water in 2002. Importance of the area [1]:

- Since the lake is located on the Via Pontica migration route and close to the Danube delta, it is one of the most important stations for birds on the Bulgarian Black Sea coast;
- Every year the wetland maintains internationally significant numbers of wintering water birds. The place provides refuge to 7 globally endangered bird species. Together with the Shabla Lake Complex, Durankulak Lake forms the largest modern wintering ground for the globally endangered species of red-breasted goose (*Branta ruficollis*) and part of one of the three places in Europe with the highest concentrations of the great white-fronted goose (*Anser albifrons*).

Fig. 1. Location of Durankulak Lake, Sentinel 2, 2019

Important habitat types for birds in Durankulak Lake which are the subject of the present study are [1]:

- Open water areas in the Large water body of the protected area;
- Open water areas in Kartaliisko (Orlovo) marsh;
- Reed massifs / water vegetation (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Important habitat types map in Durankulak Lake Protected area

The table below shows the bird species that inhabit the respective habitats.

Table 1. Important bird habitat types in Durankulak Lake

Habitats	Character of residence		
	<i>Nesting</i>	<i>Migration</i>	<i>Wintering</i>
Open water areas in the large water body of the Durankulak Lake		<i>Ph. pygmeus</i> <i>Chlidonas sp</i>	<i>Branta ruficollis</i> <i>Anser albifrons</i> <i>Ph. pygmeus</i> <i>Cygnus olor</i> <i>Cygnus cygnus</i> <i>An. platyrhynchos</i>
Open water areas in Kartaliisko (Orlovo) marsh		<i>Ph. pygmeus</i> <i>P. onocrotalus</i> <i>Aythya nyroca</i> <i>Chlidonias sp.</i>	<i>Branta ruficollis</i> <i>Anser albifrons</i> <i>Ph. pygmeus</i> <i>Cygnus olor</i> <i>Cygnus cygnus</i> <i>An. platyrhynchos</i>
Reed massifs / water vegetation /	<i>Ixobrychus minutus</i> <i>Botaurus stellaris</i> <i>Aythya nyroca</i> <i>Circus aeruginosus</i> <i>Porzana porzana</i> <i>Porzana parva</i> <i>Porzana pusilla</i> <i>Acr. agricola</i> <i>Acr. scirpaceus</i> <i>Emb. schoeniclus</i>	<i>Ph. pygmeus</i> <i>Botaurus stellaris</i> <i>Egretta alba</i> <i>Ardea cinerea</i> <i>Ardea purpurea</i> <i>Circus aeruginosus</i> <i>Circus cyaneus</i> <i>Porzana porzana</i> <i>Porzana parva</i> <i>Porzana pusilla</i>	<i>Phalacrocorax pygmeus</i> <i>Botaurus stellaris</i>

The analysis and comparison of the literature data and the results of the latest hydro chemical and hydro biological studies in the large water body of the protected area and in the Kartaliisko marsh clearly show the eutrophic to hypertrophic nature of the studied water objects. Natural succession has accelerated significantly over the last 30 years from anthropogenic activities. The natural balance in Durankulak Lake and in the Kartaliisko Marsh has been disturbed and shifted to an accelerated eutrophication process. Urgent restoration measures are needed to restore the stability of the aquatic ecosystem and avoid its rapid degradation. The main threats affect some of the most vulnerable bird species (Table 1) [2].

Some species of birds that nest in the lake (*Aythya nyroca*, *Botaurus stellaris*, etc.) depend on the small open water areas and channels among the reed massifs, and the spills in the periphery of the waterfowl massifs (as nesting and feeding sites). Increased eutrophication leads to clogging and overgrowth of these channels and open water areas, and a decrease in water level to the absence of spills. Populations of all nesting birds in the wetland are concerned about the excessive presence of humans and grazing livestock.

Remote sensing methods are a good approach for establishing the current state and season dynamics of the lake.

Data and Methods

Satellite data from the Sentinel 2A and Sentinel 2B satellite platform of the European Space Agency's Copernicus programme were used for the present study [3, 4]. Input data for the period - December 2019 to July 2020 are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Input data

Year	Satellite	Date
2019	Sentinel 2A	09/12
2020	Sentinel 2B	02/02
2020	Sentinel 2B	28/03
2020	Sentinel 2A	07/04
2020	Sentinel 2A	27/04
2020	Sentinel 2A	26/06
2020	Sentinel 2A	16/07

Satellite image processing includes:

Primary processing of satellite data:

- Creation of composite images, necessary for further processing and analysis;
- Vectorization of the protected area and the main types of habitats in the lake (according to NATURA 2000 data);
- Crop the protected area for each of the satellite images;
- Calculation of water areas in the lake.

Secondary processing of satellite data:

- NDVI calculation. Based on the input composite images from Sentinel 2, Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) was generated [5, 6, 7]. NDVI in addition to the vegetation assessment and for the accurate identification of reed massive in the Durankulak Lake was used:

$$(1) \quad NDVI = \frac{\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{RED}}{\rho_{NIR} + \rho_{RED}}$$

ρ_{NIR} = the spectral reflectance measurements acquired in the near infrared band

ρ_{RED} = the spectral reflectance measurements acquired in the red band

- For a precise assessment of the dynamics of the seasonal state of Durankulak Lake, a model of TCT (Tasseled Cap Transformation) images were obtained as results for implementation of the proposed approach. After the TCT model, the decomposition of each of the Tasseled Cap components – Brightness (BR), Greenness (GR) and Wetness (W) was made, based on which the spatial distribution graphs for each of the components were plotted [8];
- A spatial distribution of the three components of the earth's surface was made. It is shown in the form of graphs by months (for the data from the satellite Sentinel 2). They are obtained from the model for the orthogonal transformation [8, 9].

Results

- Satellite images of Durankulak Lake for the period December 2019 – July 2020.

Fig. 3. Satellite images of Durankulak Lake, Sentinel 2

The real state of Durankulak Lake from the satellite images (Sentinel 2) are shown on the figures above. The images are in the visible spectral bands, which serve for subsequent assessments and analyzes of the site.

- Assessment of water areas in Durankulak Lake

An assessment of the areas of the two open water bodies in Durankulak Lake was made - the Large water body and the Kartaliisko marsh. The assessment after precise vectorization of the water areas was made. The table below shows their areas for the observed months, and the results are shown in the following graphs (Fig. 4).

Table 3. Areas of the open water bodies in Durankulak Lake

Date	Large water body	Kartaliisko (Orlovo) marsh
09/12/2019	210.117 ha	33.6883 ha
02/02/2020	215.315 ha	33.94 ha
28/03/2020	221.867 ha	39.3147 ha
27/04/2020	221.835 ha	40.2426 ha
26/06/2020	213.437 ha	33.3613 ha
16/07/2020	205.072 ha	33.0684 ha

a) Large water body areas

b) Kartaliisko marsh areas

Fig. 4. Areas of open water bodies in Durankulak Lake

The figures above show that the areas of both water bodies in the protected zone begin to increase in March, remaining the same in April. Respectively, the Large water body area in March is 221,867 ha, in April it remains almost the same. The Kartaliisko marsh area increases from December 2019, where it is 33,688 ha to 40,242 ha in April. In the following months (June and July) there is a decrease in the area of both open water bodies. Respectively, for these months the area of the Large water body decreases to 205,072 ha per month, and the Kartaliisko marsh to 33,068 ha. Accordingly, the reduction of water areas leads to the gradual development of vegetation in them, represented mainly by reeds.

- NDVI;
NDVI in Durankulak Lake is calculated on the basis of composite satellite images. The results are shown in the figures below:

Fig. 5. NDVI index of Durankulak Lake

NDVI of Durankulak Lake for the period December 2019 - July 2020 was shown on the figures above. There is a clear trend towards a decrease in water area and overgrowth, especially in the Kartaliisko marsh (Fig. 5 b). This was noticed in March, when the water area of the swamp was still large. The most significant overgrowth was observed in June and July (Fig. 5 e, f). For the Large water body the appearance of vegetation was also observed in the months of March and April on the periphery of the area, which gradually decreases in the following months. This also leads to a reduction of its open water area. This may be due to the drought during the summer months.

- Spatial distribution of the tested components Brightness and Wetness
The decomposition of the Tasseled Cap components – Brightness (BR) and Wetness (W) are shown in the following figures:

Fig. 6. Spatial distribution of Brightness and Wetness

From the Spatial distribution of the Tasseled Cap components – Brightness and Wetness the following can be seen: During the first months observed, the spatial distribution between the two components remained relatively unchanged, in the months of December and February. In March there is a gradual dominance of the Brightness (soil) component, which maintained in the following months, most significantly in July (Fig. 6 f). In this period the water areas significantly decreased.

- Spatial distribution of the tested components Greenness and Wetness
The decomposition of the Tasseled Cap components –Greenness (GR) and Wetness (W) in the following figures are shown:

Fig. 7. Spatial distribution of the tested components Greenness and Wetness

From the Spatial distribution of the Greenness and Wetness the increasing of Greenness was noticed mostly in April (Fig. 7d). The Greenness component continues to increase in the following months. In July, the open water areas in the territory of the Durankulak Lake significantly decreased and the Greenness (vegetation) component dominated over the water (Fig. 7f).

- Spatial distribution of Greenness by months
The distribution of the Greenness (vegetation) component, which is compared by month for the observed period from December 2019 to July 2020 was shown on the figures below:

Fig. 8. Spatial distribution of Greenness component by months

The comparison of the Greenness component from the TCT transformation model by months for the observed period shows the development of vegetation in the Durankulak Lake territory. For the period December 2019 - March 2020 their distribution by months was constant (Fig. 8 a-b). For the months of March / April (Fig. 8 c) a predominance of vegetation in April was observed. For the next period - the months of June and July this trend is maintained with the dominance of vegetation for each subsequent month (Fig. 8 d, e).

Conclusion

The study monitoring shows the seasonal dynamic of Durankulak Lake. The results obtained show that there is a significant overgrowth of the open water areas in the territory of the Durankulak Lake and the reduction of their areas. This is established mostly in the months of April-July, when it is the active phase of vegetation. This leads to expansion of the reed massifs in the lake and to gradual eutrophication of the water bodies that reduces their area. This trend, if observed every year, will lead to a gradual reduction of the open water areas and hence to the loss of valuable habitats. It is necessary to carry out regular seasonal monitoring of the lake so that some conservation measures can be taken. The vegetation observations are mainly for higher aquatic vegetation represented mainly by reeds. The presence of biogenic nutrients in the water comparable to the presence of reeds vegetation will be necessary observed in future studies.

These results are important in order to assess what measures are needed to prevent reed overgrowth in the lake in the future. The present study shows a methodology for monitoring the seasonal state of Durankulak Lake, which can help to better management the territory and preserve vulnerable habitats tips.

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